

INTERACTIVE COURSEWARE TO SUPPORT BLENDED LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Covid-19 has been a game-changer in engineering education at the higher education level. Even beyond the pandemic, blended learning is there to stay. The design, execution, and delivery of blended learning can be supported by a plethora of fast-developing educational technology.

In this paper we share the experience of the evolution of one engineering course "Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence" from a rather traditional design strongly relying on face-to-face interaction to a fully blended technology-supported course.

In particular, we share the experience of how an interactive courseware platform called "Nextbook", which allows students and teacher to directly interact on the course material, supported the design, implementation, and delivery. Student experiences measured using a questionnaire are supplemented with teacher experiences to present the following "lessons learnt": A well-chosen platform can help students find clear structure in a mix of types of material, and social annotation features make it possible to connect discussion and questions and answers directly to the course material. Further efforts are needed for engaging students to actively use the features of interactive courseware platforms.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Covid-19 has forced all teachers to rethink their education and most often forced them to move their education fully online. As we are now moving beyond the pandemic phase, it becomes clear that returning to the more traditional formats with a lot of face-to-face teaching is unlikely. Students have discovered the virtues of streaming, lecture videos, and other aspects of online learning. While reasons can be of pragmatic nature (less commuting, more sleeping, etc.) students also indicate pedagogic reasons (rewatching explanations of difficult content, more efficient handling of available time, etc.). The challenge for the future is how to create high quality blended teaching, that foster rather than destroy the social aspect of learning. Learning is a social event. Social constructivism, a sociological theory in educational sciences, clearly states that knowledge is constructed through interaction with others [1]. Discussing course material with others is shown to be related to better understanding and higher academic achievement [2]. Nevertheless, it is found to be challenging to ensure students participate in online discussions [2]. The creation of online learning communities could foster students' participation, by for instance allowing for social annotations [3].

In this paper we explore one example of how an interactive courseware platform with possibilities for social annotation can be used to shape blended learning, and how it supports social interactions in this process. This paper builds on the experience of the case studies of using social annotation platforms to connect discussion to course materials reported in [4].

2 PLATFORM, CONTEXT, AND IMPLEMENTATION

Fig. 1. Part of the outline of the online course material of Uncertainty in AI as available on the Nextbook platform

2.1 Nextbook

In the context of the Erasmus+ project Co-created Interactive Courseware (CiC), we explore the new interactive courseware platform Nextbook (www.Nextbook.be) and develop pedagogical use cases, teachers guides, and learning analytics to support the use of interactive courseware on Nextbook and in general. Nextbook (<http://nextbook.be>) is a free, online platform for “social reading” of textbooks, which envisions social construction (co-creation) in the future. Teachers can upload their textbook, augmented with video, 3D models, quizzes, etc. This augmented textbook

immediately serves as a basis for social learning. Nextbook offers flexible reading on any platform as the book is transformed using web technology offering automatic scaling, free choice of font and text size, dark mode, etc. It also has functionality for reading out loud, a nice supplement on top of a dyslexia-friendly font for students with reading disabilities or challenges. Students can use highlights to mark important parts and even generate automatic summaries from these highlights. They can also add personal notes for later reference. From the social interaction point of view, they can select part of the text, image, formulate, ... and start a discussion from this or ask a question. Questions or comments can be responded to in a chat-like manner and liked (up-voted).

Fig. 2: Slides as used in the video, with the opportunity to discuss/ask questions.

2.2 Context

This paper focuses on the application of Nextbook in the context of blended learning in the 4 ECTS course Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence, offered in the Advanced Master program of Artificial Intelligence at KU Leuven, Belgium. KU Leuven is a highly ranked research-intensive university both regarding research and education. The master of Artificial Intelligence is a multi-disciplinary one-year master that recruits many international students. Typically, the course of Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence has around 250 students, and a high success rate of around 85%. Students entering the course have diverse background, with different levels of experience and skills in mathematics, probability calculus, and programming. Although some digitization was taken place before covid-19 (lecture recordings and video solutions of exercises), covid-19 forced the course to go fully online. To ensure a good online and flexible experiences, the two teachers of the course decided to replace the live lectures with a set of videos, where each video focuses on a particular topic. The lecture time slot itself was used for an online weekly Q&A session and elaboration of some additional examples.

After the initial fully online higher education, we have now moved to a new era of blended education. Teachers are expected to still offer online alternatives, but also provide on-campus activity of students. Rather than moving back to the traditional lectures with recordings, the teaching team decided to move to a fully blended format. The video material allowing the student to learn all the content of the course,

were kept but now supplemented with weekly on-campus Q&A sessions (that was livestreamed to accommodate for sick students or students not able to travel). During the weekly on-campus Q&A session, a quiz with exercises support interactive practicing of the course content, was done with the students.

Fig. 3. A video as made available in Nextbook

2.3 Implementation

On the Nextbook platform an outline of the course was created allowing students to get a structured overview of the course content (Fig. 1). Each chapter represents one lecture that corresponds to the content a student must cover in one week. Within each lecture, sections were created for the different topics. For each topic, one video was created (Fig. 3). To allow students to discuss about or ask questions on the material covered, the slides used in the video were added below the video. A student could then add a remark or question next to the slide (Fig. 2).

Students were instructed to digest the material connected to a lecture before the Q&A session and to ask their questions at latest half a day beforehand, in order to allow the teachers to prepare the Q&A session. Answers to the questions were not only provided during the on-campus and livestreamed Q&A session but also in the Nextbook platform itself (Fig. 2).

3 METHODOLOGY FOR EVALUATION

Experiences were collected from the students in two ways: using the universities official Course/Teacher evaluation, and using an online dedicated survey, both were administered in the semester after students took the course.

The **official Course/Teacher evaluation** consisted of a fixed set of 12 questions that students rate on a scale from 1-6, of which 4 were related to the approach of delivering the course material in Nextbook: (Q1) There was sufficient consistency in

the course structure; (Q2) The study materials helped me process the subject matter; (Q3) I could ask someone of the teaching staff for additional explanation; (Q4) I was satisfied with the way the circumstances due to the corona crisis were dealt with in this course. Additionally, students could also leave open remarks in two categories (what did you like and what could be improved).

To get additional feedback on the use of the Nextbook platform in the course an **additional online survey** was sent out to all students in the course with questions targeting the use of Nextbook in the course and potential future use and improvements of Nextbook.

4 RESULTS OF SURVEYS

Fig. 4: Results of custom online student survey (N=33) – part 1.

Fig. 5: Results of custom online student survey (N=33) – part 2.

4.1 Official Course/Teacher evaluation

43 students (26%) responded to the official course/teacher evaluation. The course was found to be highly consistent in structure (Q1: 5.28/6), and the material to be very supportive (Q2: 5.53/6). The opportunity for asking questions was rated very highly (Q3: 5.38/6), and it was indicated that the course dealt well with the corona circumstances (Q4: 5.47/5). Hereby the evaluation is in the top quartile of other courses evaluated with a similar student population at the university. In the open comments Nextbook was mentioned on some occasions, all in a positive manner “Nextbook was a very good online learning platform where we could directly ask question about a specific slide!”, “coherent online lecture material”, “Also, the recorded lectures as they were structured in Nextbook platform provided a great way

to find quickly any part of the study material.”, and “Online book with direct questions”.

4.2 Student survey

Fig. 4- Fig. 6 present the results of the custom online student survey (N=33). The open comments of the students are used in the discussion and recommendations below.

Fig. 6: Results of custom online student survey (N=33) – part 3.

5 DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Overall, the way Nextbook was used in the course was appreciated by the students (Fig. 4) and was found to be easy to use (Fig. 4). As some students indicate doubts about the added value of Nextbook (Fig. 4), the discussion below digs deeper on some specific themes.

5.1 Structured integration of material

The points that was most appreciated about the use of Nextbook in the course is the **structure** that was provided. 13 out of 31 students explicitly mentioned the structured as positive aspect. Some examples: “It was very structured, which was handy for understanding and learning the material.”; “Very structured.”; “Also, it’s very structured, which can give me a better understanding of the whole structure and timeline of the course. “Everything is structured by topic which makes it much easier to digest and process. Also, easier to later find the relevant video in case of any questions”.

Furthermore, **the integration of the different types of material** (video and slides) was acknowledged: “Having the whole course videos and slides blended together in the same place and quickly accessible”; “I wish more courses would use this type of combination of video lectures and slides on such a platform.”; “[...] Also the mix of video and slides was particularly helpful.”

Nextbook is not the only platform that could provide structure and integration of different types of material, and one could argue that the use of a platform as

Nextbook is “overkill” if it is only there for structure and integration. Therefore, the next sections dig deeper on the more social parts of the learning that Nextbook aims to strengthen.

Our recommendation Integration of different types of material in one overviewable structure is worth investing in, as students clearly value these aspects.

5.2 Connecting discussion to the course material

Students indicate that it is good to be able to ask questions or discuss directly connected to the course material (Fig. 5): “Ability to ask questions specific to parts of the course.”; “Students can post questions on a particular slide”; “Also nice to see questions of other students at the relevant slide instead of mixed together on a discussion forum.” One student indicates this is in fact the only added value of the platform “As a mechanism of asking questions, it worked, but that was about the only value of the platform for me.” The teachers however observed that only about 20 different students regularly used the discussion or questions/answer throughout the course. We hypothesize that most students look at the discussions and questions and answers without actively participating, as students indicate it is helpful to see other students’ questions/discussions connected to a slide (Fig. 6), and that they are less positive about the possibility to participate in answering questions and joining a discussion (Fig. 6) and liking or rating questions and answers (Fig. 6). The social aspect of the platform is therefore underused. A student states it nicely as follows: “I think this [asking questions connected to the course slide] exactly is one of the more powerful features. Reading the questions in the “flat list” of Toledo [the VLE of the university] makes it sometimes difficult to “link” the question with the text in the book. Having them both tied-up together would indeed be more interesting.”

The fact that students asked questions directly on the material was very helpful for the teachers in preparing their lectures and Q&A sessions. Rather than looking to a, often unstructured discussion board, the teachers could browse through the course material and immediately see which points were unclear to students. In fact, the teachers just projected the Nextbook slides with the connected questions during the live Q&A session in order to start an additional explanation.

Our recommendation Connecting the discussion to the course material is valuable and handy for the teacher, but additional efforts are required before it can be considered as real online social learning.

5.3 Future of Nextbook

Students agree that Nextbook should be used in the course (Fig. 4) as it provides added value (Fig. 4), and that it has potential to be used in other courses (Fig. 5). When asked about which Learning Analytics aspects would be helpful to be added (Fig. 6), students are more conservative. While they believe that seeing the “hot items” could be of value, they disagree that getting feedback on their activity level, or motivational messages (Fig. 6). Like one student expresses, potential reasons are the level of experience and self-regulation of master students and the fear to induce additional stress: “Personally, I liked its simplicity. I think that adding the suggested extra information would just add stress when you happen to have a busy week. Closer following other people’s discussions might also add to that stress. In my experience most master’s students know how important it is to keep up with the material and can find discussions in case they have a question.” While individual

students do see value in such approaches to get additional feedback “Indeed give feedback on how you are performing at the moment and what to do better”.

Our recommendation Learning Analytics should be used with care and should primarily focus on showing students what are students are working on.

5.4 Other aspects

Different students express the concern that the course material on Nextbook is only available online, which causes more screen time, and makes them fear that the material will not be available anymore after they graduate.

The more interactive nature also triggers with some the fear to have to spend more time on the course “What I suppose, is that doing it in a classical style would require less time, while the notebook style is quite more dynamic but needs more time to spend to enjoy it fully.”, while other even ask for more interactive features “Maybe in the middle of some chapters some practical questions could be asked. I’m either multiple choice questions form or blank filling form.”

While Nextbook was in general found easy to be used (Fig. 4), some students still experience difficulties “I had difficulties with adding a question to the slides. I followed the instructions but for some reason it did not work.”. “About 40% of the chapters didn't function properly for me. For instance, I couldn't put the video to full screen or change the volume of sound through the browser.”. Or “I did not really use the ask questions function. It was my fault, but I forgot my password each time, which is required to enter comments or questions”. This is surprising as technical assistance was available throughout the entire course and every single technical issue that was reported was solved within a very short time frame.

Our recommendation Provide ample opportunity for students to ask for technical assistance, and to look for ways students could also use the course material offline and download after the course for future reference after they finished the course.

6 CONCLUSION

Interactive courseware has a potential to support blended learning. A well-chosen platform can help students find clear structure in a mix of types of material (e.g., videos, text, and slides). Furthermore, social annotation features of such platforms make it possible to connect discussion and questions and answers directly to the course material. While this feature is valued a lot by teachers and students, only a minority of the students actively uses it, and therefore we cannot say that there is already a real online learning community supporting online learning. To realize the full potential of social learning, additional efforts are required to trigger discussions and exchanges among students.

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